

Seismic assessment approaches for mass-dominant sliding contents: The case of storage racks

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ABSTRACT: The typical view of seismic performance of structure-content systems is one of segregation: Contents are assumed to be of low mass relative to the supporting structure, leading to a separate treatment of the two, whereby one first analyzes the structure and then subjects any contents to the resulting peak floor acceleration responses. Racking structures are of the exact opposite persuasion, having massive “palletized” contents that can slide on top of light cold-formed steel frames, with Content-Structure-Sliding Interaction (CSSI) governing global and local response. In support of assessment and design, three approaches are investigated to capture CSSI: (i) introducing friction sliders per pallet and running nonlinear response-history analysis, (ii) increasing the model viscous damping and using elastic response-history analysis, and (iii) reducing the horizontal seismic loads in tandem with modal response spectrum analysis. Each comes with its own challenges and modelling/analysis needs, offering different levels of accuracy (or no appreciable capability at all) when assessing the actual sliding displacement of contents. Three case studies are employed to calibrate empirical relationships for damping amplification and seismic load reduction, largely removing the bias of simpler alternatives (ii) and (iii), respectively, to level the ground for future code applications.

KEYWORDS: steel racking systems, sliding, friction, pallets

1 Introduction

Steel pallet racking systems are civil engineering structures used to store goods and materials before their distribution to the public. They comprise thin-walled cold-formed members that carry high live loads, by far greater than their self-weight. They come in a variety of dimensions and typologies^[1], with the most common being the Adjustable Pallet Racking (APR) system (see Figure 1). Contents are not mechanically connected to the racking system, but are placed on pallets, boxes, containers or even hanged. As a result, the seismic response of racks is characterized by a Content-Structure-Sliding Interaction (CSSI) that typically does not appear in conventional buildings. Specifically, during seismic excitation, inertia forces are initially transferred from the goods to the rack by means of static friction forces acting on the surface between, e.g., the pallet and the supporting beams in case of an APR. Depending on the applied excitation, this stabilizing mechanism may not be adequate to restrain the contents, which can then *slide* relative to the rack. CSSI is multi-faceted, offering both detrimental and beneficial effects. Before the onset of sliding, the transfer of forces between adjacent pallet beams or rails and the immobile pallets themselves offers a horizontal diaphragm effect^[2,3]. Additionally, after content sliding is initiated, sliding friction sets an upper boundary to the inertia forces transferred to the racking system, effectively reducing the horizontal mass of the contents that needs to be accounted for deriving the seismic forces. This reduction of the apparent inertia of the rack due to sliding of the goods is akin to a *seismic isolation mechanism* and henceforth it will be referred to as such.

On the other hand, excessive content sliding can lead to localized damages due to impacts on structural components or even global collapse due to contents falling off (Figure 2) and crushing adjacent frames. The first phenomenon is prevalent in the down-aisle direction where frame columns, so-called uprights, can arrest excessive pallet displacements. Content fall-off is especially critical in the transverse direction of the racking system, the so-called cross-aisle direction (Figure 1), as there are no uprights to prevent the goods from sliding off. It is also noted that even moderate levels of sliding may result to long downtimes in automated rack warehouses. Therein, robotic systems store and retrieve the pallets, thus, whenever a unit load slides beyond the systems’ tolerances, operation ceases until manual re-adjustment of pallets takes place. There are even more aspects to CSSI that cannot be fully discussed herein. For example, Adamakos et al.^[4] found that, contrary to current code assumptions (e.g., EN16681^[5]), the friction force is

52 unequally distributed between the two edges of a pallet resting on supporting beams, with higher forces appearing on
53 the leading edge in the direction of sliding.
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Figure 1: Primary structural components of an Adjustable Pallet Racking (APR) system and definition of the down/cross-aisle directions (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.A.).

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Figure 2: Partial collapse of an adjustable steel rack due to pallet falling during the Christchurch earthquake of 2011^[6].

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57 Of particular interest in accounting for CSSI in design and assessment are (i) the beneficial effect of reduced horizontal
58 inertial mass for estimating lateral loads, and (ii) the estimation of sliding displacements to avoid fall-off and/or
59 impact. Current seismic codes do not offer a tool to predict the latter, as it is related to absolute floor (or *load level*, in
60 rack parlance) accelerations, for which a conventional Multi-Response Spectrum Analysis (MRSA) is not able to
61 provide any information (for alternatives see [7], [8], [9]). On the other hand, they incorporate the positive effect of
62 sliding isolation using the inertial mass reduction factors.

63 For example, in USA, the Rack Manufacturer Institute, RMI^[10], specification accounts for sliding by applying a
64 multiplication factor of 0.67 to reduce the seismic mass of contents, regardless of the friction coefficient of the contact
65 surface or the seismic intensity. On the other hand, in Europe, EN16681 adopts an E_{D1} factor to modify the design
66 spectrum in the context of MRSA, given as:

$$E_{D1} = \max\{0.4, \mu/Sa(T_1) + 0.2\} \leq 1.0 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

67 where μ is the reference value of the unit-load/beam friction coefficient, T_1 is the fundamental period of vibration of
 68 the racking structure in the considered direction, and $Sa(T_1)$ is the ordinate of the elastic spectrum defined in EN1998-
 69 1^[11], in units of g.

70 Eq. (1) is based on a limited study from the SEISRACKS^[12] European project. Elastic time-history analyses were
 71 performed on a low-rise APR system along the down-aisle direction, using 3 loading situations, 3 levels of spectral
 72 acceleration and 7 artificial accelerograms. It was found that the 0.67 mass reduction factor suggested by RMI is close
 73 to the average value of the inertial reduction predicted by the time-history analyses, however it can be unconservative
 74 for moderate seismicity levels, where seismic intensities are not high enough to overcome friction and initiate sliding.
 75 While the E_{D1} factor given by EN16681 is a conceptually better approach over the seismic-intensity-independent 0.67
 76 mass reduction suggested by RMI, it is still questionable whether it can safely be applied for designing along the cross-
 77 aisle direction or for high-rise racking systems, where the contribution of higher modes is increased.

78 To address such issues in CSSI, we shall offer three comprehensive solutions for accounting for CSSI in rack systems:

79 (i) Nonlinear RHA for MDOF structures, employing realistic friction sliders under nonlinear response-history
 80 analysis,

81 (ii) Linear RHA for MDOF models, employing increased viscous damping to account for sliding “isolation” of pallets.

82 (iii) MRSA of elastic models, using reduced seismic loads to account for the effect of sliding.

83 To fully explain the differences among the three approaches, and understand their capabilities, let us first delve into
 84 the simplest of CSSI problems and the available methods to treat them.

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86 2 RHA for SDOF systems

87 CSSI for SDOF structures

88 Newmark’s Sliding Block Analysis^[13] (NSBA) was first introduced to calculate the permanent displacement of soil
 89 slopes during seismic loading. It uses the time history of accelerations that exceed friction to derive sliding
 90 displacement via a double integration. Let us consider a body with mass m (i.e., the pallet) resting on a platform (i.e.,
 91 the racking system), as illustrated in Figure 3. Assuming a Coulomb friction model^[14] the contact surface between the
 92 body and the platform is characterized by a friction constant μ , which linearly relates the developed friction F_T with
 93 the normal force acting on the body N , i.e., $F_T = \mu N$. Whenever the external/inertial forces acting on the body exceed
 94 T (in absolute value), the body starts moving relatively to the platform and Newton’s third law of motion gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma F &= ma_{rel} \Rightarrow ma_{plat} - F_T = ma_{rel} \Rightarrow ma_{plat} - \mu mg = ma_{rel} \Rightarrow \\ a_{rel} &= a_{plat} - \mu g \Rightarrow a_{rel} = a_{plat} - a_y \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

95 where a_{rel} is the relative-to-the-platform acceleration of the body, a_{plat} is the absolute acceleration of the platform
 96 and $a_y = \mu g$ is the *yield* (or sliding-onset) acceleration, which determines whether the body starts sliding on the
 97 platform or “re-sticks” to it. The term ma_{plat} is introduced because we are examining the motion of the body relatively
 98 to the platform, which is a non-inertial frame of reference.

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Figure 3: Idealized model of a body with mass m sliding with a friction constant μ on a moving rigid platform.

101 Instead of employing NSBA to calculate the relative motion of the body in post-processing of the structural analysis
 102 results, one may directly employ “flat slider” finite elements that explicitly consider the effect of sliding and friction,
 103 such as the flatSliderBearing element of OpenSees^[15] coupled with a Coulomb friction model. Let us consider a sliding
 104 body on top of a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) cantilever, essentially a two-degree-of-freedom (2DOF) slider-on-
 105 cantilever model with a total mass of M at the top, comprising three nodes (Figure 4(a)): Node 1 that has a fix support
 106 and nodes 2 and 3 that have the vertical and the rotational DOFs restrained. Nodes 1 and 2 are connected by a beam-
 107 column element of EI stiffness, while nodes 2 and 3 by a flat slider with friction constant μ . By assigning a very high
 108 value of EI , i.e., a 2DOF system with $T = 0$ sec, one can recover the simpler model of a body sliding on the ground
 109 (or on a platform rigidly connected to the ground) resembling Figure 3. An example of such a system appears in Figure
 110 5, illustrating the absolute acceleration and sliding graphs for a seismic excitation with a PGA that exceeds the yield
 111 acceleration of $a_y = 3 \text{ m/s}^2$. Notably, the absolute acceleration diagram of the model with the flat slider is bounded
 112 between $[-3, +3] \text{ m/s}^2$, while the one employed with NSBA is by definition identical to the imposed ground motion,
 113 as the 2DOF system has a period of vibration $T = 0$ sec. As expected, the analytical model can achieve almost perfect
 114 results without the need of a more expensive numerical integration.

Figure 4: Numerical model of a 2DOF system of a cantilever beam with a flat slider at the top, showing (a) a case where the whole mass can slide ($m = M$), and (b) a case where only a portion m of the total mass M can slide, while $M - m$ is attached to the beam.

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Figure 5: Absolute acceleration and sliding diagrams of a mass sliding with friction coefficient $\mu = 0.3$ on top of a rigid platform (period $T = 0$ sec), comparing the predictions of NSBA (SDOF system with rigidly connected mass, where sliding is estimated in post-processing) against the 2DOF flat slider model of Figure 4(a) (Landers 1992, Station BAKER FIRE, PEER NGA2^[16], scaled by 3.28).

Figure 6: Absolute acceleration and sliding diagrams of a 2DOF system with period $T = 0.7$ sec, $\mu = 0.3$, and $m = M$ (100% of mass can slide) comparing the predictions of NSBA (SDOF system with rigidly connected mass, where sliding is estimated in post-processing) against the 2DOF flat slider model of Figure 4(a) (Landers 1992, Station BAKER FIRE, PEER NGA2, scaled by 3.28).

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118 The accuracy of NSBA is in question when one analyzes non-rigid platforms, essentially 2DOF systems with $T >$
 119 0 sec. Figure 6 illustrates the absolute acceleration and sliding graphs for a system with $T = 0.7$ sec ($M = 10,000$ kg
 120 and $\mu = 0.3$) where 100% of mass M can slide, using the same excitation as in the body-on-rigid-platform problem
 121 presented previously. To employ Newmark's approach, nodes 2 and 3 (Figure 4(a)) are rigidly connected, turning the
 122 2DOF into an elastic SDOF of mass M , and NSBA is applied on the absolute acceleration timehistory estimated at the
 123 top of the platform. The maximum sliding predicted by NSBA is almost two times greater than the one derived by the
 124 2DOF slider-on-cantilever model, while the difference is even greater for the residual displacements. The source of
 125 error can be identified by comparing the absolute accelerations of the two models: NSBA is based on the full mass
 126 and inertia of the system, while the slider constantly changes the "apparent" inertia of the 2DOF model (i.e., the mass
 127 that is moving with the supporting structure) from 0 to 10,000 kg, depending on whether the mass slides or not,
 128 leading to smaller displacement estimates.

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Figure 7: Comparison of NSBA ("Approximated") with a 2DOF slider-on-cantilever ("Exact"), in terms of the predicted sliding for a system with $T = 0.7$ sec and $\mu = 0.3$. The 16%, 50% and 84% fractiles of 30 ground-motions are shown, for m/M within 1% – 100%.

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131 While NSBA is not suitable for cases where the entire system mass can slide, it can still be quite accurate for typical
 132 buildings, where the mass of the contents is a small portion of the total. This can be demonstrated by modifying the
 133 slider-on-cantilever model of Figure 4(a), to a model with a sliding mass m on node 3 and a non-sliding mass $M - m$
 134 on node 2, as shown in Figure 4(b). Figure 7 compares NSBA with the flat slider in terms of predicted sliding, using
 135 a set of 30 ordinary records selected & scaled to be hazard-consistent at the intensity with a 10% in 50 years probability
 136 of exceedance for Van, Turkey^[17], and m/M ranging within 1% – 100%. For values of $m/M < 0.05$, NSBA gives
 137 near perfect results, as CSSI has a minor effect. Values of $0.05 < m/M < 0.8$ lead to an unbiased median, yet a
 138 steadily increasing standard deviation, either on the low side (16%) or the high side (84%). In other words, NSBA
 139 would not be an accurate, or even safe alternative (for $m/M > 0.30$), despite being unbiased. On the other hand, for
 140 high $m/M > 0.8$ the sliding overestimation grows exponentially, starting from a mean value of 110% (median of
 141 100%) for $m/M = 0.80$, up to 170% for $m/M = 1.0$. Still, how this translates to a multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF)
 142 racking system with multiple load levels and modes of vibration is not apparent.

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144 **Equivalent damping ratio**

145 As shown previously, for high values of m/M , NSBA overestimates considerably the sliding in a 2DOF system with
 146 $T > 0$ sec. In addition, as the effect of sliding is not considered explicitly in the analysis, the calculated stress resultants
 147 and deformations are also overestimated. Rather than mandating the use of nonlinear sliders in response history
 148 analysis, we propose the adoption of an equivalent damping ratio (ξ_{eq}) for linear models in place of, e.g., the
 149 conventional 3% used in racks. Similarly to Jacobsen^[18], there is no direct physical meaning behind this equivalent
 150 damping, only an empirical adjustment of elastic response to account for the apparent reduction of inertial forces due
 151 to sliding. It is a convenient method to implicitly decrease the seismic loads imposed on a structure without affecting
 152 its eigenmodes or eigenvalues.

153 The equivalent damping ratio should depend both on the seismic motion under consideration and the friction constant.
 154 For relatively mild excitations, ξ_{eq} should be equal to the default 3% value and increase for more vigorous vibrations.
 155 Moreover, for the same seismic motion, a wooden pallet (lower μ) should have greater ξ_{eq} than a plastic or steel pallet.
 156 Additional parameters such as the pulse period of pulse-like ground motions, or the dominant period of the excitation
 157 in general, may be influential when considering the response under a specific record^[19]. Still, they are not considered
 158 as they cannot be easily introduced in practical applications. Essentially, the sliding displacement, and consequently
 159 the ξ_{eq} , of a 2DOF system with $m = M$, period T , and friction constant μ , is tested against the single variable $Sa(T)/\mu$
 160 that was selected as the normalized Intensity Measure (IM) for the effect of pallet sliding, with $Sa(T)$ being the
 161 spectral acceleration of a linear elastic oscillator with period equal to T . Our intention is to derive an expression for
 162 ξ_{eq} on the 2DOF and employ it to approximate the response of MDOF racking systems.

163 Eleven 2DOF systems with periods within [0.3, 2.5] sec were selected. A total of 105 “ordinary” (i.e., no directivity,
 164 no long duration) ground motion records were selected from the PEER-NGA strong motion database^[20] and scaled to
 165 eight normalized intensity levels of $Sa(T)/\mu$ in (1, 3]. Finally, four friction constants were employed to account for
 166 different contact surfaces between the pallets and the racking structure within [0.15, 0.40]. For each level and 2DOF
 167 system, the equivalent damping ratio was adjusted by steps of 0.5% until the mean sliding predicted by NSBA matched
 168 the flat slider model. Figure 8 shows an example of application for a 2DOF with $T = 0.75$ sec, $Sa(T)/\mu = 2.25$, and
 169 $\mu = 0.30$. Using linear regression analysis on the 352 individual points (11 models \times 8 levels \times 4 friction constants)
 170 of $Sa(T)/\mu - \xi_{eq}$ the following formula was derived (Figure 9):

$$\xi_{eq} = \min \left\{ 3\%, \quad 5.82\% \frac{Sa(T)}{\mu} - 3.97\% \right\} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

171 with an error standard deviation of $\sigma_{\xi_{eq}} = 0.0061$ or 0.61%. It is noted that even though Eq. (3) was fitted for $1 \leq$
 172 $Sa(T)/\mu \leq 3$, the ξ_{eq} results are identical for different values of μ thanks to the normalization of the IM; thus, the
 173 validity of the expression can be extended to larger values of $Sa(T)/\mu$ if needed.

174 The results of the RHAs can also be used to investigate how the period of the system T affects the maximum sliding
 175 displacement. Figure 10 shows the mean values of sliding for the aforementioned eleven 2DOF slider-on-cantilever
 176 systems with $\mu = 0.30$, subjected to 105 ground motions and 8 levels of IM. In general, the higher the period of the
 177 2DOF system, the greater the sliding^[21]. Indeed, it has been shown analytically that the maximum displacement of a
 178 sliding mass depends approximately on the square of the dominant period of the excitation^[19], which for sliding of
 179 contents it is practically equivalent to the period of the supporting rack that dominates the narrow-band floor/level
 180 excitation^[22].

Figure 8: Boxplots of the ratio of the sliding displacement predicted by NSBA (“Approximated”) over the estimate of the 2DOF slider-on-cantilever (“Exact”), for a system with $T = 0.75$ sec, $\mu = 0.30$ and $Sa(T)/\mu = 2.25$, using 105 ground motions (red asterisks indicate the mean values). The optimal $\xi_{eq} = 9.5\%$ results to a mean ratio ~ 1.0 .

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Figure 9: Linear regression analysis for the relation of $Sa(T)/\mu$ with the equivalent damping ratio, ξ_{eq} , selected to optimally match NSBA with the 2DOF slider-on-cantilever.

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Figure 10: Mean values of sliding displacement for 11 2DOF systems with different periods of vibration and $\mu = 0.30$, subjected to 105 ground motions and 8 levels of IM.

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184 **3 RHA for MDOF systems**

185 **CSSI for MDOF structures**

186 Flat slider elements can be employed in the numerical model of an MDOF rack to directly simulate CSSI. In the case
 187 of APR (Figure 1) or APR-like systems where one pallet is supported by two pallet beams, a horizontal force H acting
 188 on the unit load produces a pair of overturning vertical forces equal to $H \cdot e_v$, due to the vertical eccentricity, e_v ,
 189 between the center of gravity of the unit load and the beams, as shown in Figure 11. These overturning forces can
 190 increase the upright axial force. Ideally, to consider this phenomenon a set of 5 nodes is required at each load level;
 191 Nodes 1-3, 2-3 and 4-5 are connected by “rigid” elements, while nodes 3-4 by a flat slider. This sub-system of nodes
 192 1-5 is then connected to the upright frame by rotational hinges in nodes 1 and 2. Still, this complex model is not needed
 193 in all cases. For example, when multiple pallets are resting on pallet or rail beams, the overturning forces are countered
 194 by the adjacent pallets, as shown in Figure 12. Such cases are the down-aisle direction of racking systems with multiple
 195 pallets per bay, or the cross-aisle direction of multi-depth systems (EN16681).

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Figure 11: Modelling of pallets along the cross-aisle direction of an APR system using flat sliders and rigid elements.

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Figure 12: When multiple pallets are resting on pallet/rail beams, the pair of overturning forces $H \cdot e_v$ produced by the vertical eccentricity of the pallet and the supporting beams is cancelled by its adjacent pallets.

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For low-rise racking systems with a limited number of pallets, one can employ the aforementioned sub-system of flat sliders and dummy elements to simulate the behavior of each pallet, without affecting considerably the robustness of the numerical model. On the other hand, the numerical simulation of all pallets on a multi-depth high-rise racking system may require hundreds of flat slider elements, leading to convergence difficulties.

In general, as pallet sliding is an issue only in the cross-aisle direction (where pallets can slide off the rack), one can take advantage of the similar/repeated upright frames to substantially reduce the model size^[23]. Herein, we chose to consider a single upright frame instead of the full cross-aisle frame, as they have very similar periods and modes of vibration. By closely matching the dynamic characteristics of the full frame, the sliding behavior of pallets can be well approximated. For the case of racking systems that also act as supporting structures for the roof, so-called Automated Rack Supported Warehouses (ARSWs), axial horizontal springs are considered at the top level of the single upright frame to account for the roof lateral restraint (Figure 13). The stiffness of the axial springs was calibrated to match the first five eigenmodes and eigenvalues of the full cross-aisle frame. Finally, another simplification strategy to reduce the number of DOFs of the numerical model is to substitute the single upright frame with a “stick” model comprising Timoshenko beam elements that account for the shear flexibility of the system^[23]. Due to the aforementioned issue of overturning forces, when the focus is on the design of the upright frame, rather than on the assessment of the sliding displacement, this final simplification can only be accurately applied in cases where said forces are counteracted by multiple pallets, e.g., multi-depth cross-aisle frames (Figure 13). When only sliding is concerned, the stick simplification is always a viable option.

Figure 13: Substitution of the full cross-aisle frame of multi-depth systems with a single upright frame or a single stick that employs horizontal axial springs at the top, to simulate the lateral restraint offered by the roofing system.

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Five modelling approaches

Five modelling approaches will be tested to simulate CSSI for MDOF systems in the context of a response-history analysis, each characterized by a different level of accuracy and computational efficiency (see Table 1). The first one, termed the Full Model (FM) approach, comprises flat sliders to simulate the contact surface between the rack and the

unit loads. It is the benchmark modelling approach to assess the accuracy of the other simpler options. The second technique, the Stick Model (SM), also incorporates flat sliders but the upright frame is substituted with a stick model to decrease the number of DOFs. The third approach, the Newmark's block Model (NM), does not use any special elements or implicit methods to account for the pallet sliding; the absolute floor accelerations are recorded and an NSBA is conducted for each load level.

The fourth approach, namely the Newmark's block with equivalent Damping Model (NDM), also uses NSBA together with an equivalent damping ratio to capture the isolation effects of pallet sliding. Specifically, for each record the first and second spectral accelerations are calculated, namely $Sa(T_1)$ and $Sa(T_2)$, respectively. Then the corresponding $\xi_{1,eq}$ and $\xi_{2,eq}$, can be derived by Eq. (3) and a mean equivalent damping ratio is calculated as:

$$\bar{\xi}_{eq} = \frac{\xi_{1,eq} + \xi_{2,eq}}{2} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

A more natural choice would have been to apply $\xi_{1,eq}$ and $\xi_{2,eq}$ to the first and second mode instead of using a mean value. Indeed, Rayleigh damping formulation allows different damping ratios to form the damping matrix:

$$[C] = a_0[M] + a_1[K] \Rightarrow \begin{Bmatrix} \xi_i \\ \xi_j \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1/\omega_i & \omega_i \\ 1/\omega_j & \omega_j \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

where:

$[C]$, $[M]$ and $[K]$ the damping, mass and stiffness matrix, respectively;

ω_i and ω_j the angular frequency of modes i and j (not necessarily the first and second mode);

ξ_i and ξ_j the damping ratio of modes i and j ;

a_0 and a_1 the mass and stiffness coefficients of the Rayleigh damping formulation.

Solving Eq. (5) for a_0 and a_1 leads to:

$$a_0 = \frac{-2\omega_i\omega_j(\xi_i\omega_j - \xi_j\omega_i)}{\omega_i^2 - \omega_j^2}, \quad a_1 = \frac{2(\xi_i\omega_i - \xi_j\omega_j)}{\omega_i^2 - \omega_j^2} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

For $\xi_i = \xi_j = \xi$, the classical Rayleigh coefficients are derived^[24]:

$$a_0 = \frac{2\omega_i\omega_j}{\omega_i + \omega_j} \xi, \quad a_1 = \frac{2}{\omega_i + \omega_j} \xi \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

Using Eq. (7), a_0 and a_1 are always positive values as they involve multiplications and additions of positive terms. On the other hand, the coefficients derived from Eq. (6) can also be negative, which leads to negative damping matrices that are not physically meaningful. To illustrate this issue with an example, a typical case of a racking system is selected with periods of vibration $T_1 = 1.5$ sec and $T_2 = 0.5$ sec and a constant damping ratio in the first mode $\xi_1 = 3\%$. Figure 14 illustrates the values of a_0 and a_1 for increasing ξ_2 , using Eq. (6). As the difference between ξ_1 and ξ_2 grows, i.e., the ratio ξ_2/ξ_1 increases, the mass coefficient a_0 becomes negative and thus the contribution $a_0[M]$ to the damping matrix leads to a dynamically unstable system. To avoid such issues, applying the averaged damping of Eq. (4) uniformly to both modes is preferable.

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Table 1: Selected modelling approaches, indicating the use of flat slider elements, equivalent damping or none.

Model	Description	Flat sliders	Equivalent damping ratio
1 FM	Full Model	✓	✗
2 SM	Stick Model	✓	✗
3 NM	Newmark's block Model	✗	✗
4 NDM	Newmark's block Model with Mean ξ_{eq}	✗	✓
5 NWDM	Newmark's block model with Weighted Mean ξ_{eq}	✗	✓

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Figure 14: Rayleigh damping coefficients for $\xi_1 = 3\%$ and ξ_2 varying from 3% to 30%.

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253 The fifth modelling approach, the Newmark's block with Weighted mean equivalent Damping Model (NWDM), also
 254 incorporates an NSBA framework together with an equivalent damping ratio, similarly to the NDM, with the
 255 difference that a weighted mean of the $\xi_{1,eq}$ and $\xi_{2,eq}$ is used:

$$\xi_{w,eq} = w_1 \cdot \xi_{1,eq} + w_2 \cdot \xi_{2,eq} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

256 where w_1 and w_2 are weights for the first and the second mode, to take into account the higher influence of the first
 257 mode:

$$w_1 = \frac{m_1^*}{m_1^* + m_2^*}, \quad w_2 = \frac{m_2^*}{m_1^* + m_2^*} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

258 where m_1^* and m_2^* are the effective modal masses of mode 1 and 2, respectively.

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260 Description of case studies

261 To illustrate the application of the proposed method, three case studies will be examined. The first example consists
 262 of a multi-depth ARSW that has been designed by professional engineers according to EN1993^[25], EN15512^[26] and
 263 EN16681 to be installed in the city of Van, Turkey, for a peak ground acceleration of $a_g = 0.3 \text{ g}$ and a friction constant
 264 $\mu = 0.3$. The overall plan dimensions are 65.80 m \times 71.50 m in the cross- and down-aisle direction, respectively,
 265 while the total height is about 25.60 m. There are nine load levels, each comprising four storage cells of 13 unit-load
 266 capacity (Figure 15), thus each cross-aisle pallet frame supports up to 468 pallets. Load levels 1 to 2 are for 1000 kg
 267 pallets, 3 to 5 for 800 kg and 6 to 9 for 600 kg.

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Figure 15: Cross-aisle view of the multi-depth Case Study 1, consisting of 24 “K-type” upright frames and a connecting shallow roof truss (units in meters).

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Herein, a single cross-aisle pallet frame is considered, comprising 48 uprights, connected in pairs to form 24 “K-type” upright frames of 1.35 m width (Figure 15). The cross-section area of the diagonal braces of the upright frames was reduced to 10% to account for the reduced shear stiffness due to their bolted connection^[27]. To decrease the number of involved flat sliders and corresponding DOFs, the simplification procedure discussed earlier is followed. Thus, a single upright frame is isolated and properly calibrated axial springs are employed at the top nodes of the model to account for the effect of the roof (Figure 13). Regarding the mass distribution, the most critical upright frames of a 13-pallet storage cell lie one frame away from its edges and they are assumed to support 2 pallets per load level.

The second case study consists of a medium-rise back-to-back indoor APR system with eight load levels, designed to be installed in a facility at Aspropyrgos, Greece, with a peak ground acceleration $a_g = 0.24 g$ and a friction constant $\mu = 0.3$. Load levels 1 to 5 and 7 are designed to carry 3×480 kg unit loads per compartment, while load level 6 and 8 carry 3×640 kg and 3×240 kg, respectively. To accommodate a variety of unit loads, the vertical distance between the load levels is not constant. In the cross-aisle direction (Figure 16(a)) two upright frames are connected with 3 spacers (at 1.33, 4.93 and 8.53 m from the floor), to form the back-to-back storage system. Each individual upright frame has an X bracing pattern up to 3.13 m distance from the floor and it continues upwards with a D system, as the seismic loads are lower. The cross-section area of the diagonals was also reduced to 10% of their gross area, to account for the flexible bolted connection. Herein, a single upright frame is considered, assuming that the spacers do not offer adequate stiffness and the two upright frames can be analyzed individually. Finally, the third example comprises a low-rise back-to-back APR system which was derived by considering the four upper load levels of Case Study 2 (Figure 16(b)), but using a friction constant $\mu = 0.37$. Table 2 summarizes the cross-sectional properties for the main structural members of all case studies, while Table 3 contains the periods and mass participation factors for the first six modes of each structure. The high-rise ARSW (Case Study 1) has a relatively low mass participation factor on the first mode and thus, the contribution of higher modes on the CSSI is expected to be more significant. On the other hand, the low-rise APR (Case Study 3) comprises a first-mode-dominant structure, while the medium-rise APR (Case Study 2) is an in-between scenario of the other two examples.

Figure 16: Cross-aisle view of: (a) the medium-rise APR Case Study 2 and (b) the low-rise APR Case Study 3 (units in meters).

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Table 2: Cross-section properties of structural members. Cross-section areas are rounded to the 3rd digit while moments of inertia to the 5th.

Member	Case Study	Section	Steel Grade	A (mm ²)	I _y (mm ⁴)
Lower upright	1	Ω	S350GD	1300	3000000
Upper upright	1	Ω	S350GD	900	2000000
Lower upright frame diagonal	1	C	S350GD	500	150000
Upper upright frame diagonal	1	C	S350GD	300	340000
Roof truss lower chord	1	I	S350GD	1640	5410000
Roof truss Upper chord	1	Ω	S350GD	680	610000

Roof truss bracing	1	C	S350GD	330	110000
Upright	2, 3	Ω	S350GD	580	480000
Upright frame diagonal	2, 3	C	S280GD	100	20000

C = Channel section, Ω = Ω section, I = I section

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299

Table 3: Periods and mass participation factors for the three considered case studies along the cross-aisle direction.

Mode #	Case Study 1		Case Study 2		Case Study 3	
	Period (s)	Mass Part.	Period (s)	Mass Part.	Period (s)	Mass Part.
1	1.79	66%	1.02	75%	0.47	86%
2	0.62	17%	0.30	17%	0.16	11%
3	0.32	5%	0.17	4%	0.09	2%
4	0.23	2%	0.12	2%	0.08	1%
5	0.17	1%	0.09	0%	0.07	0%
6	0.07	8%	0.08	0%	0.06	0%

300

301 Seismic hazard and record selection

302 For each site, a set of 30 natural records was used (set #1 for Van^[17] and set #2 for Athens^[28]), that match the
 303 Conditional Spectra (CS)^{[29],[30],[31]}, using the geometric mean of spectral accelerations, *AvgSa*, as the IM^[32]:

$$AvgSa(T_{Ri}) = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n Sa(T_{Ri}) \right)^{1/n} \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

304 Each *Sa* value in Eq. (10) is actually the geometric mean of both horizontal components, rather than an arbitrary
 305 selection of one of the two. Generally speaking, period T_{Ri} can be selected as linearly spaced within a range of [T_L ,
 306 T_H], where T_L is a low period near the minimum second mode of building to be investigated and T_H is a high period
 307 that is near 1.5 time their maximum first mode period. Herein, for reasons of simplicity we employed a single period
 308 range for both sites of [0.3s, 3.0 s] with an increment of 0.2 s. Figure 17 illustrates the *AvgSa* hazard curves of Van
 309 and Athens. Crossing the hazard curves with a horizontal line at the design level (i.e., 10% in 50 years), the
 310 corresponding IM in Athens is equal to 0.11 g while in Van 0.24 g, or more than twice.

311

Figure 17: Hazard curves for the sites of Athens and Van, using *AvgSa* as an IM.

312

Table 4: Selection of seismic input for Case Studies 1, 2 and 3.

Probability of exceedance	Case Study 1	Case Study 2, 3
2% in 50 years	-	set #2 (IM = 0.25 g)
3% in 50 years	set #1 (IM = 0.43 g)	set #2 (IM = 0.21 g)
5% in 50 years	set #1 (IM = 0.33 g)	set #2 (IM = 0.16 g)
10% in 50 years	set #1 (IM = 0.24 g)	set #2 (IM = 0.11 g)
20% in 50 years	set #1 (IM = 0.19 g)	-

IM: $AvgSa(0.30 - 3.0 \text{ sec})$, set #1: 30-records set for Van, set #2: 30-records set for Athens

314

315 To compare the five modelling approaches, a series of RHAs is conducted using the aforementioned 30-records sets
 316 for multiple IM levels. Table 4 shows the selection of seismic input for each case study, presented in terms of
 317 probability of exceedance. In general, racks are characterized by low or non-existent ductility, therefore brittle failures
 318 tend to govern the response. For reasons of checking sliding displacements of large magnitude, we have chosen herein
 319 not to simulate such failures, assuming instead that members remain elastic and the only source of nonlinearity comes
 320 from geometric considerations (i.e. P- Δ effects). In general, this is considered to be a more severe test of the different
 321 modelling formulations, as it leads to larger sliding displacements. Allowing earlier failures or even material
 322 nonlinearity would either stop the analysis earlier, or reduce sliding due to the beneficial reduction of (absolute and
 323 relative) peak accelerations at each floor (see for example ATC-120 NIST^[33] report).

324

325 Comparison of modelling approaches

326 Each case study was analyzed using 4 scales of IM and 30 ground-motions (see Table 4), for a total of 360 RHAs.
 327 The four “Approximated” quantities, resulting from the SM, NM, NDM and NWDM approaches, were compared with
 328 the “Exact” approach, FM. From each RHA, the maximum (over height and time) base shear, roof drift, interstorey
 329 drift and sliding displacement were derived, and the “Approximated/Exact” (or A/E) ratios were estimated. A useful
 330 approximating approach would be considered to have a mean A/E close to 1.0, thus being unbiased, with low
 331 dispersion of the overall results, as large dispersions indicate higher uncertainties.

332 Figures 18(a) to 18(d) illustrate the resulting ratios using boxplots. It should be noted that the range of sliding ratios
 333 can be misleadingly large; low “Exact” values of pallet movement of, e.g., 0.1 mm coupled with an “Approximated”
 334 value of 0.3 mm will lead to an A/E of 3.0. This seems quite high, but it is of little engineering significance as the
 335 pallets in both models remain practically idle. To alleviate this issue, we chose to only consider sliding ratios
 336 corresponding to “Exact” displacements higher than 5 mm.

337 The SM approach shows excellent predictive ability, both in terms of mean value and coefficient of variation (CoV)
 338 for all recorded structural responses. The only statistic that may be cause for worry is the $CoV = 0.41$ in the pallet
 339 sliding ratio; this is expected, as the absolute floor accelerations are quite variable themselves^{[34],[35]}. Nevertheless, as
 340 the record-to-record variability dominates the dispersion of pallet sliding, it is safe to consider this error to be of
 341 secondary importance. Thus, one can easily choose to substitute FM with the more frugal SM, reducing the
 342 computational cost and gaining in numerical robustness.

343 On the other hand, the NM approach overestimates all responses, giving a mean A/E of 1.37 for the base shear, 1.46
 344 for the roof drift, 1.43 for the interstorey drift and 1.73 for the pallet sliding. Recalling Figure 7, NSBA on a 2DOF
 345 slider-on-cantilever with $T = 0.7 \text{ sec}$ showed a similarly mediocre performance, overestimating sliding by a factor of
 346 1.70 when m/M is greater than 0.95, as expected for a typical rack. Instead, employing the equivalent damping ratio
 347 ξ_{eq} per the NDM approach reduces the bias and the variability, bringing mean A/E values closer to 1.0 and decreasing
 348 CoVs. Contrarily, the NWDM approach, where higher weight is applied to the first mode of vibration per Eq. (9), is
 349 inferior to the NDM. Perhaps this should not be totally unexpected as local responses (such as sliding) tend to be
 350 heavily influenced by higher modes, whereas the weighting of the modes in NWDM was derived per their contribution
 351 to the roof displacement, disproportionately favoring the fundamental mode.

352

Figure 18: Boxplots of the “Approximated/Exact” ratio of (a) Base Shear, (b) Roof Drift, (c) Interstorey Drift and (d) Sliding, for all the $30 \times 12 = 360$ RHAs shown in Table 4 (the FM approach was considered the “Exact” solution, and the rest four “Approximated” were compared against it).

353

354 **4 MRSA for MDOF systems**

355 **Reduction of lateral loads for simplified CSSI**

356 Targeting practical code-compatible design or assessment applications, where MRSA is the method of choice, the use
 357 of a lateral load reduction factor similar to E_{D1} (Eq. (1)) is a simple and effective way to account for CSSI. Comparing
 358 the results of the FM approach with NM, is equivalent to comparing the effect of sliding versus non-sliding masses.
 359 By dividing said results, one can calculate a reduction factor to convey the effect of CSSI per each RHA. When thus
 360 considering the resulting base shears, one can determine by proxy a reduction factor that can be applied to the design
 361 spectrum to estimate the “effective” lateral loads as $E_{N1} = V_{b,FM}/V_{b,NM}$, where $V_{b,FM}$ and $V_{b,NM}$ are the maximum
 362 recorded base shear of the FM and the NM approach, respectively. Three IMs were considered, namely $Sa(T_1)/\mu$,
 363 $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, and their geometric mean $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$. Figure 19(a) to Figure 19(c) illustrate the E_{N1} – IM
 364 data points for all the 360 RHAs, fitted with a simple linear regression, $E_{N1} \approx b_0 + b_1 \cdot IM$. A higher $R^2 = 0.54$ (with an
 365 error standard deviation of $\sigma = 13.64\%$) is achieved using $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$ as the IM, with respect to $R^2 = 0.43$
 366 and $R^2 = 0.36$ when using $Sa(T_1)/\mu$ and $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, respectively. The resulting expression for E_{N1} , bounded within
 367 $[0.4, 1.0]$ for compatibility with EN16681, is:

$$E_{N1} = \max \left\{ 0.4, -0.1966 \cdot \sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu + 1.0995 \right\} \leq 1.0 \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

368

Figure 19: Linear regression analysis for E_{N1} (FM/NM base shear reduction) given the IM of (a) $Sa(T_1)/\mu$, (b) $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, and (c) $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$.

369

370 In general, it should be understood that the code-compatible approach of E_{N1} is a practical yet fairly limited solution,
 371 compared to RHA with flat-sliders or ξ_{eq} . If Figure 19 is not enough warning, Figures 20(a) to 20(c) and Figure 21(a)
 372 to 21(c) illustrate the reduction of the roof drift and the maximum interstorey drift, respectively. One can observe that
 373 the reduction of the roof drift is strongly related to $Sa(T_1)/\mu$, a well-known behavior of any building-like structure
 374 with a relatively dominant first mode. On the other hand, the reduction of the maximum interstorey drift is also
 375 sensitive to $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$, as the effect of higher-order modes becomes significant locally, e.g., at the lower
 376 levels of a racking system where the maxima tend to appear. Thus, in general we expect the E_{N1} approach to work
 377 well for base shear, but become less accurate for roof drift, and even worse for story drifts.

378

Figure 20: FM/NM roof drift reduction given the IM of (a) $Sa(T_1)/\mu$, (b) $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, and (c) $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$.

379

Figure 21: FM/NM maximum interstorey drift reduction given the IM of (a) $Sa(T_1)/\mu$, (b) $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, and (c) $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$.

380

381 Finally, as a side note, Figure 22(a) to Figure 22(c) show scatter plots of the maximum recorded pallet sliding for each
 382 of the 360 RHAs. These are the results of the FM models, as MRSA cannot be used to assess sliding. One can observe
 383 that sliding is loosely dependent on any of the three considered IMs. Essentially, there is a high record-to-record
 384 variability in sliding responses that cannot be easily captured: Small changes in the absolute floor accelerations may
 385 lead to large deviations on the corresponding goods movement. Another significant observation is that in most cases
 386 the taller rack experiences greater sliding displacements than the shorter, similarly to what was found for 2DOF
 387 systems of long versus short periods (Figure 10).

Figure 22: Pallet sliding prediction via RHA with flat sliders given the IM of (a) $Sa(T_1)/\mu$, (b) $Sa(T_2)/\mu$, and (c) $\sqrt{Sa(T_1)Sa(T_2)}/\mu$.

388

389 Comparison of MRSA approaches

390 As shown previously, the most efficient method to implicitly consider the positive effect of pallet sliding in the context
 391 of a RHA, without using any special slider elements, is to adopt the equivalent damping ratio of Eq. (4), i.e. the NDM
 392 approach. This equivalent damping ratio can also be used to modify the design spectrum in an MRSA, for example
 393 by using the damping modification η -factor of EN1998:

$$\eta = \sqrt{10/(\xi_{eq} + 5)} \geq 0.55 \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

394 On the other hand, one may also use the E_{N1} reduction factor given in Eq. (11) to straightforwardly decrease the design
 395 seismic forces. To compare the two approaches, the high-rise ARSW case study 1 is used, employing the 30-records
 396 set for the city of Van^[17], scaled to intensity levels corresponding to 3%, 5% and 10% in 50 years probability of
 397 exceedance. Five sets of analyses are conducted for all records:

- 398 (1) RHA: RHA using flat slider elements, which is considered as the benchmark.
 399 (2) MRSA- E_{D1} : MRSA using the actual spectrum of each record with 3% damping ratio, a reduction factor E_{D1}
 400 according to EN16681 given by Eq. (1) and a CQC modal combination.
 401 (3) MRSA- ξ_{eq} : MRSA using the actual spectrum of each record with the equivalent damping ratio given by Eq. (4)
 402 and a CQC modal combination.
 403 (4) MRSA- E_{N1} : MRSA using the actual spectrum of each record with 3% damping ratio, a reduction factor E_{N1} given
 404 by Eq. (11) and a CQC modal combination.
 405 (5) MRSA- $1.1E_{N1}$: A modified version of (4), where the coefficients in Eq. (11) are multiplied by a factor of 1.10.
 406 While MRSA- $1.1E_{N1}$ is expected to overestimate the average response of the rack, it is a conservative approach that
 407 may be preferable for design.

408 Geometric nonlinearities (i.e., P- Δ effects) were treated explicitly in RHA via a first-order approximation, while in
 409 MRSA their effect was incorporated according to EN16681. Specifically, modal analysis was performed by taking
 410 into account the geometric stiffness matrix, which makes the structure more flexible and thus elongates the periods of
 411 vibration. Moreover, the lateral seismic forces were multiplied by a factor $1/(1 - \theta)$, where θ is the sensitivity
 412 coefficient, calculated as:

$$\theta = q_d \cdot P_E / P_{cr,E} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

413 Where P_E is the total gravity load of the rack in the seismic design situation, $P_{cr,E}$ is the Euler critical load and q_d the
 414 displacement-related behaviour factor, assumed equal to 1.0 as the structural model does not incorporate any ductility.
 415 Figure 23(a) to Figure 23(f) show the A/E ratios, with RHA considered as the ‘‘Exact’’ result, for various response
 416 parameters.

417 The MRSA- E_{D1} analysis overestimates practically any parameter of interest, namely base shear, upright/diagonal axial
 418 forces, and roof drift, by 20% to 40%. MRSA- ξ_{eq} tends to decrease, but not nullify this overestimation, while MRSA-
 419 E_{N1} offers the best overall performance, both in terms of a nearly-unbiased mean value and smaller CoV. Given that
 420 the lower bound in MRSA- E_{N1} over RHA predictions tends to lie around 0.90, a 10% increase of E_{N1} can help achieve
 421 a higher level of safety, commensurate with the current norm represented by MRSA- E_{D1} over RHA. This is
 422 demonstrated by the MRSA- $1.1E_{N1}$ approach, which achieves a code-like lower bound (i.e., similar safety), while
 423 having reduced dispersion (i.e., lower overestimation and higher economy) when compared with EN16681.

424

Figure 23: Boxplots of the MRSA/RHA ratio of (a) maximum bottom upright axial force, (b) maximum bottom diagonal force, (c) maximum top upright axial force, (d) maximum top diagonal axial force, (e) base shear and (f) roof drift, for the upright frame of case study 1, using the 30-records set #1, scaled to 3%, 5% and 10% in 50 years probability of exceedance (red asterisks indicate the mean value while red horizontal lines the median).

425

426 5 Conclusions

427 Three different methods for tackling CSSI are offered, distinguished by their need for RHA versus MRSA analysis,
 428 as well as the level of modelling detail, requiring friction slider elements versus adjustments of damping or lateral
 429 loads. A distinct advantage of RHA-based methods is their capability to assess content sliding displacement, at the
 430 cost of requiring ground motion records. From the RHA-based methods, definitely the best results are obtained by
 431 employing friction slider elements to simulate the sliding of the pallets, with the cost of increasing the numerical
 432 complexity of the model. On the other hand, completely excluding the effect of CSSI during the execution of RHAs
 433 leads to large overestimations on the predicted mean pallet sliding (+73%) and the corresponding base shear (+37%)
 434 and interstorey drift (+43%) of the rack. To alleviate this issue while keeping the numerical model as simple as
 435 possible, it was found that a good solution is to adjust the damping ratio of the model according via a simple regression
 436 expression. Achieving the same feat of the RHA with MRSA is not easy, as it requires modal combination approaches
 437 to predict peak floor accelerations (presently available, e.g., by Moschen et al.^[8]), plus some (presently unavailable)
 438 approximation approach to covert such accelerations to sliding displacements. Still, even the lowly MRSA approach
 439 combined with the proposed empirical lateral-load reduction formula, can offer unbiased prediction of forces,
 440 moments and deformations, suitable for application within the code in tandem with the desired factor of safety. In the
 441 case study examined, the MRSAs using the E_{D1} factor of EN16681, overestimate the forces on the uprights and
 442 diagonals by 20% – 40% on average, which means that lighter (and hence more economical) sections could be
 443 potentially used. On the other hand, using the proposed E_{N1} offers better overall performance, largely removing the
 444 bias and decreasing the dispersions, while reducing the overestimation of member forces to 2% – 15% on average for
 445 a more economical design. In any case, it cannot be stressed enough that the trend for taller racking systems leads to
 446 a higher propensity for excessive pallet displacement, as racks with longer periods of vibration tend to experience
 447 larger sliding. Thus, the structural design of high-rise racking systems may need to be accompanied by a series of
 448 RHAs (or some practical equivalent), to estimate the magnitude of pallet sliding and assess whether precautions have
 449 to be taken to arrest pallet movement.

450

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462

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